

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

SKELETAL MUSCLE RELAXANT ACTIVITY OF *BOUGAINVILLEA GLABRA* LEAVES IN SWISS ALBINO MICE

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 28/03/2018

Available online

05/04/2018

Keywords

Bougainvillea Glabra,

Nyctaginaceae,

Skeletal Muscle Relaxant,

Rotarod,

Phytochemical Screening.

ABSTRACT

The current work is carried out to investigate the skeletal muscle relaxant property of *Bougainvillea glabra* (400mg/kg, p.o). Rota rod model was constructed to evaluate the activity in Swiss albino mice. The animals were randomly divided into test, standard and control. The control group received distilled water, standard group received diazepam 4mg/kg and the test group received the methanol extract. The methanol extract of *Bougainvillea glabra* significantly reduced the fall off time (5.63 secs) compared to the fall off time of diazepam treated animals (2.55 secs). The reduced fall off time observed in *Bougainvillea glabra* methanol extract treated mice indicates the motor incoordination on rotarod apparatus. Moreover, the preliminary phytochemical screening of the extract indicates that it possess various bioactive components like alkaloids, glycosides, flavonoids, saponins and tannins. In conclusion, the above results indicates that there is a need of identification and isolation of active constituents of methanolic extract of *Bougainvillea glabra* which might be responsible for the skeletal muscle relaxant activity.

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Please cite this article in press as **Sudheer Kumar Dokuparthi et al. Skeletal Muscle Relaxant Activity of *Bougainvillea Glabra* Leaves in Swiss Albino Mice. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2018;8(03).**

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INTRODUCTION

Muscle spasm is often a serious problem which is caused by the involuntary muscle contractions. Skeletal muscle relaxants are a class of drugs which can relieve spasm and spasticity. Muscle spasm generally is an acute condition which is caused by strain or sprain. The antispastic agents like baclofen are used to reverse muscle hypertonicity and involuntary jerks. For skeletal muscle spasm, antispasmodics are the drugs of choice like cyclobenzaprine¹.

Bougainvillea glabra, belongs to Nyctaginaceae, native to North Africa, South West and South Asia, and extensively cultivated elsewhere. Extensive literature review of *Bougainvillea glabra* revealed that the leaves contain alkaloids, glycosides, saponins, steroids and tannins²⁻⁴, which might be responsible for the skeletal muscle relaxant activity.

Bougainvillea glabra which is commonly known as glory of garden is an ornamental herb. Though the origin is South America it is very often in tropical and subtropical countries. The genus belongs to the family Nyctaginaceae. The name *Bougainvillea* was given in the name a French navigator, who first documented in Brazil, in 1768⁵. The flowers are scentless, very attractive surrounded by bracts which are modified leaves in fact are useful in its reproduction and spreading of pollen grains⁶.

Since there is a need to find skeletal muscle relaxant drugs, the purpose of current work is to screen the skeletal muscle relaxant activity of the plant *Bougainvillea glabra* in Swiss albino mice by rota rod apparatus.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Extraction:

The fresh plant was collected during the month of September, 2017 from Hayathnagar rural area, Hyderabad. The plants were authenticated and specimens have been deposited in the college museum. The shade dried leaves are then subjected to a coarse powder by the cutter type electric mill. Then, the powder is extracted with methanol by soxhlet's apparatus. The percentage yield was found to be 10.5%. Then the extract was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening⁸.

Experimental animals:

Swiss albino mice (20-25g) were used in the experiments. After randomly grouping them, the mice were acclimatized for a period of ten days. The mice were maintained under standard environmental conditions such as temperature ($26 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), relative humidity (45-55%) in polypropylene cages and 12hr. Dark/light cycle. The animals were fed with sufficient rodent pellet diet and water. The current study protocol was approved by the institutional animal ethics committee (IAEC) before commencement of experiment (1230/a/08/CPCSEA).

Preliminary phytochemical screening

Preliminary phytochemical screening of the methanol leaf extracts was done by the standard procedures⁷. The results are illustrated in the Table 1.

Skeletal Muscle Relaxant Activity by Rota Rod Apparatus in Swiss albino Mice

Procedure:

Animals were weighed and marked. The mice were grouped into three each having three mice and named as control(C), test (T) and standard(S). The control group received distilled water, test group received *Bougainvillea glabra* at a dose of 400mg/Kg and standard group received diazepam at a dose of 4mg/Kg. Swiss albino mice which possess the ability to remain on revolving rota rod for 5 minutes at 20rpm are selected for the test⁹. The falloff time from the rod was noted which indicates the grip strength¹⁰.

Statistics:

All the values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, the significance between control and test was analyzed by ONE way ANNOVA, followed by student t test where $P < 0.001$, $P < 0.01$ and $P < 0.05$ are considered as statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Preliminary phytochemical screening:

By using various standard procedures as described in the literature, the screening of methanol leaf extract of *Bougainvillea glabra* revealed the presence of a wide variety of phytochemicals which are depicted in the Table 1. The results shows that the plant contains tannins, flavonoids, steroids, saponins and glycosides.

Table 1. Preliminary phytochemical screening of various extracts of *Bougainvillea glabra* leaf.

Phytochemicals	n-Hexane extract	Ethylacetate extract	Methanol extract
Alkaloids	+	-	+
Glycosides	+	+	+
Terpenoids	+	+	+
Steroids	+	+	+
Saponins	+	+	+
Flavonoids	+	+	+
Tannins	-	+	+
Carbohydrates	-	-	-
Lipids	-	-	-
Proteins	-	-	-

Skeletal muscle relaxant activity

The fall off time noted in the experiment was illustrated in Table 2. The results exposed that the plant possess significant skeletal muscle relaxant activity in Swiss albino mice when compared to the control and standard diazepam in a dose dependent manner. The dose 400mg/Kg showed highest skeletal muscle relaxant activity at 30 minutes of duration. From the above results we can assume that the reported activity may be attributed to the tannins present in it. Further studies are in progress and to isolate the bioactive constituents responsible for the musculoskeletal activity.

Table 2. Skeletal Muscle relaxant activity of *Bougainvillea glabra* methanol leaf extract.

S.No	Treatment	Dose (mg/Kg)	Average fall off time in Seconds
1	Distilled Water (Control)	0.2ml	11.5
2	Methanol extract (Test)	400mg/Kg	5.63*
3	Diazepam (Standard)	4mg/Kg	2.55*

* P<0.05 was considered statistically significant.

CONCLUSION

The current study on *Bougainvillea glabra* leaf methanol extract revealed that, the leaves possess significant anti spasmodic activity in Swiss albino mice. Further studies are in progress for the understanding of the mechanism of the reported effect and to isolate and identify the bioactive compound for the skeletal muscle relaxant activity.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We are thankful to Vijaya College of Pharmacy for providing the necessary facilities for our Research.

Funding

No funding sources

Conflict of interest

Authors do not have any conflict of interest.

List of abbreviations

ANOVA	- Analysis of Variance
cm	- Centimetre
eg	- Example
h/hr	- Hour
ICH	- International Conference on Harmonization
CPCSEA	- Committee for the Purpose of Control And Supervision of Experiments on Animals
mg/kg	- Milligrams per Kilogram Body Weight
min	- Minutes
ml	- Millilitre
mL/kg	- Milliliter per Kilogram Body Weight
SD	- Standard deviation
SEM	- Standard Error Mean
°C	- degree Celsius
Mg	- Microgram
%	- Percentage

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